

PLANNING AND OPERATION OF POWER SYSTEMS WITH IMPLEMENTED JOINT EXCITATION AND REACTIVE POWER CONTROLLERS

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Abstract

Electric power systems are designed to generate electric energy economically and to transfer this energy to customers at virtually fixed voltage and frequency. Enhancing network designs to optimize service quality may involve tradeoffs between reliability and power quality. The cost of trying to fix an incompatible system after installation is hundreds to thousands of times more than addressing it in the planning stage. Power quality could be considered as the combination of voltage and current quality. Intensified monitoring of voltage and reactive state of the generating units is of most importance. Monitoring of the generating units is easier when joint excitation and reactive power controllers (JEQC) are implemented because then minimum and maximum production or absorption of reactive power can be delivered in accordance with dispatchers instructions. Currently JEQC is installed in two largest steam power plants in Serbia. In this paper results of simulations of JEQC device are presented. The analysis were carried out on a system representing operating conditions planned for year 2020. Results obtained through simulations of JEQC device ability to commit generation units in a way to obtain maximum reactive power reserve enable the use of JEQC as an efficient tool for secondary voltage control.

1 Introduction

Electric power systems are designed to generate electric energy economically and to transfer this energy over transmission lines and distribution networks with the maximum efficiency and reliability for delivery to customers at virtually fixed voltage and frequency. The optimal level of investment in designing such a system is to be achieved by means of a tradeoff between reliability and costs. Due to the deregulation of the electricity industry, there is no longer a single vertically structured system but a number of independent companies linking electricity generation with end users and competing among themselves for customers. It is essential to the future of these companies to target investments towards the network improvements that will be most effective. This can only be achieved through a careful quantification of service reliability and

power quality and the inclusion of these results in network design.

In addition to the deregulation of electrical power industry customers' expectations regarding the quality and reliability of their electricity supply are high and steadily rising. The emphasis has been on fixing existing problems rather than preventing future problems. The cost of trying to fix an incompatible system after installation is hundreds to thousands of times more than addressing it in the planning stage. Power system performance is determined by the entire electrical system from the generator to the device powered.

1.1 Voltage conditions in Serbian Power System

Power quality could be considered as the combination of voltage and current quality. In operation of the transmission system the following periods with the typical voltage conditions occur: winter period with extreme consumption (when there is a lack of generator voltage-regulating capacity, voltages are within the permitted limits or move towards the lower limit), summer period (with high consumption which causes high temperatures and problems with cooling generators and the step-up transformers, leading to the great lack of voltage-regulating capacity of the generator and voltage values within the permitted limits or move towards the lower end, with partial transition to unacceptable voltage levels) and spring period with the lowest consumption (especially around Easter and May 1 when during night periods unauthorized extremely high stress levels occur). In the case of extremely high voltage certain activities including absorbing reactive power by generators, exclusion of certain lines and putting the unit transformer in neutral position in coordination with neighbouring transmission system operators are used to preserve N-1 safety criteria. In the case of extremely low voltages maximum production of reactive power in generators, by reducing the active power at the expense of reactive power, adjusting the position of the control transformers and even suspending delivery of electricity to the necessary extend are actions that Serbian Transmission System Operator (TSO) uses. In both cases intensified monitoring of voltage and reactive state of the generating units which have to work in a safe zone is of most importance.

The consequence of the market deregulation process is a tendency of TSO to manage the power transmission system with the primary criteria to maximize profit or to minimize the transfer of reactive power (Q), thus leaving enough space for the transfer of active power (P), as well as the minimization of transmission losses in the power system due to the mandatory purchase of losses by the TSO. At the same time the criteria determining the quality of electricity supply should be satisfied [1], [2], [3]. Voltage quality tests indicate that values are at a satisfactory level, but there is a tendency to deterioration.

In the first version of the transmission system Grid Code requirements were expressed by the stress-regulatory capacity of generating units through graphics $U_g - \cos \varphi$ (where U_g is voltage on the generator). These rules further requested that the step-up transformer should not be a limiting factor in contributing to the generator voltage regulation unit. Currently applicable version of national Grid Code requirements is presented via graphics $U_m - \cos \varphi$ (U_m is generator voltage at the network connection point), which included the above request to the step-up transformers. This graph is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1 Currently applicable version of national Grid Code requirements

Figure 1 shows that the requirements according to the generating units range from capacitive operation with $\cos \varphi = 0.9$, when the voltages in the transmission network (on the collectors to which a step-up transformer is attached) are at the nominal value or higher (up to the maximum allowable the value of short-permitted modes), and on the other side to inductive operation with the $\cos \varphi = 0.85$, when the voltages on these buses are in the range 0.9-1.1 r.j. for the 400 kV network or from 0.85 to 1.15 r.j. in case of the 220 kV and 110 kV transmission network. In accordance with the Energy Law, TSO concludes contract for the provision of support services to production units, where one of the ancillary services and providing capacity for voltage regulation. The aforementioned contract covers all generating units. Currently, payments for this type of ancillary services are based on the prices determined by the Energy Agency of the Republic of Serbia. It is not

established by measuring the performance of individual plants, and there is no reduction in the invoice in case of failure to provide the agreed scope of services or contractual penalty.

1.2 Reactive power sources in power system

Synchronous generators are the basic elements for voltage regulation in the system. Voltage regulation is done by changing the generator excitation current and at the same time it changes the value of the Electromotive force (EMF) induced in the stator windings. An increase in the induced EMF leads to an increase of reactive power that generator provides to the transmission system. In case of a need for less reactive power minimisation of induced EMF is performed. Synchronous generators are not inexhaustible sources of reactive power.

Most transformers come equipped with taps on the windings to adjust either the voltage transformation or the reactive power flow through the transformer. During the year different seasons could be detected depending on voltage profiles in the transmission network. For each season it is possible to determine the best position of the tap which would insure that the voltages vary in range of values in accordance with the Grid Code on a daily basis. It is necessary to define the season for which the optimal position of the tap is determined. To define a season, it is necessary to identify periods of the year with a similar voltage profiles. On the basis of the generation unit power chart allowed reactive power of the plant, Q_{min} and Q_{max} , can be determined for the corresponding value of the generator voltage. It is also possible to determine the range of permissible value of voltage on the high voltage side of the transformer that will provide plant operation within the permitted limits in accordance with the capability chart of the generator [16],[17],[18],[19]. When defining an optimal tap position voltage variations in the transmission system should be taken into consideration. Optimal position of the tap is being determined depending on reactive power flow through the transformer. The goal is to make sure that voltage vary in a defined range of values on a daily basis by fully utilising reactive capacity of the generator.

The Flexible Alternating Current Transmission System (FACTS) devices represent a dependable solution to solve the task of advanced control of transmission system in new operating environment. The FACTS technology is largely based on application of the high voltage power electronic switches that enable modulation of key parameters that govern the operation of transmission systems including series and shunt impedances, currents, voltages, phase angles and real and reactive power flows. They are built from safe materials and they do not produce any kind of emissions or waste during the operation that may pollute the environment [20]. FACTS devices are capable of performing a range of different tasks and functions that contribute to safe, secure and economic operation of

power systems. Series and shunt FACTS can be used effectively for voltage stability and reactive power compensation. They can greatly enlarge the region of voltage stability for a wide range of loading conditions and play an essential role in improving the voltage profile of the system. The Thyristor Controller Series Capacitor (TCSC) and Static Var Compensator (SVC) were used in [21] for the advanced VAR planning in a power system network in order to prevent voltage collapse following a contingency, while at the same time ensuring that the bus voltages remain within the statutory limits. The same devices were employed in [22] to enhance voltage stability of the network. Enhanced voltage support by an SVC was also reported in [23]. TCSC also contributes to better power system voltage stability for a wide range of loading conditions [24]. Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC) and Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) can improve the voltage stability of the network [25],[26]. In addition to voltage stability improvement the UPFC demonstrated excellent voltage control and series reactive power control capabilities [25], [27].

1.3 Joint excitation reactive power controller

In SPP TENT A a newly developed device JEQC was installed a few years ago which ensured at all times, maximum Q reserve uniformly distributed between generators, according to the current operating state of the generator and other equipment. Provision of the required amount of reactive power reserve from power plants in the power system as well as the distribution of reactive power between generators in power plants is carried out using the algorithm based on (1),(2),(4),(5), [6],[7]. The reactive power reserve of the power plant was calculated using (1):

$$k_{plant} = \frac{Q_{request}}{Q_{max_{plant}} - Q_{min_{plant}}} \quad (1)$$

and the reactive power reserve of each generator using (2):

$$k_{igen} = \frac{Q_i - Q_{imax}}{Q_{imax} - Q_{imin}} \quad (2)$$

The situation regarding generators has become critical because they are now forced to operate in a capacitive area of capability curve for the most of the day. These operating regimes are characterized with the occurrence of the problems related to the temperature rise in the generator stator core. Temperature problems are of a local nature and they lead to uneven distribution and increased density of the magnetic fields in end core area due to operation of generators in the capacitive area. Temperature monitoring devices which are placed in stator core area give a general picture of the stator temperature distribution. Critical hot spots temperature in this zone can be much higher than the measured temperature of the core and can lead to serious

degradation of stator winding insulation in a relatively short period of time [8].

The owners of SPP also reported the uneven heating of the generators that occurs when maintaining maximum reactive reserves. It should be noted that the JEQC maintains the same distance from the capacitive limits on all generators in the power plant and such favourably affects the heating of the stator and in results the rotor and the stator windings being more heated when generator is operating in inductive area of capability chart. The possibility of obtaining the maximum Q reserves at the PCC should be specified through Grid Code and adequately compensated to plant owners [9]. Also important to note is that the synchronous generators are the only source of dynamic reactive power in the Serbian power system and that reactive power should be available for compensation during transients. There are the opposing requirements with respect to managing the transmission system operation related to minimisation of the losses at one hand and the stability of power system on the other. Furthermore, the uniform heating of the generators involves the loading of generators proportionally to their nominal apparent power (3) and, on the other hand, it is necessary to respect the criteria of maintaining optimal voltage and reactive reserve at all times.

$$k_{igen} = \frac{\sqrt{P^2 + Q^2}}{S_{ni}} \quad (3)$$

Due to implementation of a large number of renewable energy sources in the electricity systems the ENTSO-E defined requirements for the plant as a whole, as opposed to defining requirements for each generator. In this sense, a JEQC observes power plant as a virtual generation unit, in terms of voltage and reactive power, with a single Q-V characteristic.

TSO manages the bus voltage where the facility is connected and defines ranges of voltage values for a given generation level of reactive power. The JEQC device, when implemented manages the Q-V characteristic. In this way, TSO may perform minimization of losses in the transmission system by controlling voltages at the connection points of the power plants, in case that the power plant is equipped with JEQC device. At the same time JEQC provides the maximum reactive power reserve that power plant can provide to the system, in order to prevent the occurrence of voltage collapse [10],[11],[12].

1.3.1 Recorded value of active power, reactive power and voltage in SPP TENT A

Currently JEQC is installed in two largest steam power plants in Serbia, SPP "Nikola Tesla A" and SPP "Nikola Tesla B", which are electrically close to each other. Two study cases were performed to demonstrate JEQC performance. The first when JEQC was turned off (30th of January 2014) and with JEQC in operation (31th of December 2014). The value of active power, reactive power and voltage that are recorded on 30th of January

2014 at 7:30 am are considered as initial values. The initial bus voltages were: $V_{220}=227.9$ kV and $V_{400}=404$ kV. Figures 2 and 3 shows that generators response to system disturbance leads to unequal reactive power distribution when generators in SPP are different (generators 1 and 2 differ from generators 3 and 4).

Figure 2 Reactive power responses for 30_01_2014. JEQC is turned off, the equivalent Thevenin EMF of the 220 kV network changes in steps 213 kV - 200 kV - 190 kV

Figure 3 Reactive power responses and generator load coefficients k_Q for 30_01_2014 at SPP TENT A, JEQC is turned off

Figure 4 Reactive power responses for 31_12_2014 when JEQC is turned on ($V_{220ref}=227,4$ kV, $V_{400ref}=402,8$ kV, $s=0,03$ at SPP TENT A buses), the equivalentnet Thevenin EMF of the 400 kV network changes in three steps: 400 kV-390 kV-370 kV

Figure 5 Reactive power responses and generator load coefficients k_Q in SPP TENT A and TENT B for 31_12_2014., JEQC is turned on

From Figure 4 and 5 it is obvious that the JEQC is capable to maintain the maximum reactive reserve under changing load conditions with uniform Q allocation across generators connected at same busbars.

2 Methodology

From the above it can be seen that it is necessary to intensify activities regarding voltage regulation to improve its quality. The main objective is to provide voltages in the normal operating range of the transmission system with taking into consideration the impact of joint excitation reactive power controller (JEQC) where it exists. Simulations of JEQC device ability to commit generation units in a way to obtain maximum reactive power reserve were performed. Analyses were conducted for different operating conditions, typical for longterm planning studies.

The Scenario Outlook & Adequacy Forecast (SO&AF) presents scenarios included in the Ten-Year Network Development Plan (TYNDP) in compliance with Regulation (EC) n. 714/2009 . The SO&AF is based on national data as provided by each ENTSO-E member TSO or a national organization responsible for data collection for different TSOs ("source-data"). It sets out 3 scenarios for generation and demand: the "EU2020" scenario is derived from the National Renewable Action Plans (NREAP) in compliance with the European 3x20 objectives or from other governmental / national documents /policies; Scenario B ("Best Estimate") is based on the expectations of TSOs; Scenario A ("Conservative") is derived from Scenario B, taking into account only the generating capacity developments which are considered secure [13].

The analysis were carried out on a test system representing operating conditions (different critical regimes-winter max, summer max and summer min) planned for year 2020 for case study of parallel operation of two excitation and reactive power controllers (JEQC) installed in two largest steam power plants in Serbia, SPP "Nikola Tesla A" and SPP "Nikola Tesla B".

The main purpose of the JEQC is to perform a slow voltage control at PCC of the plants by automatically adjusting the levels of generated reactive power of the SPP's generators while i) ensuring the uniform and synchronized response of all participating generators in case of power system disturbances, ii) preventing generators from operating in forbidden areas of the capability chart where overheating of stator core can occur, iii) restoring operating point of the generator after a major disturbance to the pre-fault value. The case study considered the Q-V controller outputs at the high voltage side of the SPP's step-up transformer. The parameters used are given in the official technical documentation provided by the owner of the SPP.

Simulation models of Southeast Europe region consists of complete model of the Republic of Serbia transmission network with 400 kV, 220 kV and 110 kV voltage levels (in this model consumers are modelled as loads on 110 kV voltage level based on measurements from SRAAMD data base scaled according to adequacy forecast) and neighbouring countries transmission network with 400 kV and 220 kV voltage levels with Greek transmission network where, in addition to 400 kV voltage level, 150 kV voltage level is modelled.

As a starting point for a model of South-East Europe, SECI model in PTI PSS@E software package for year 2020 was used [14]. This model was updated and adapted for the needs of the TYNDP. The regional model includes electric power systems of the following countries: Austria, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Macedonia, Hungary, Romania, Serbia, Montenegro, Greece, Slovenia, Italy, Ukraine and Turkey. For the global balance-reference node plant Ziller in Austria was selected, due to its distance from the analysed areas, in order to reduce the influence of mathematical approximations on output. The regional model was used for the calculation of totals for all countries and the values of power flow on the interconnecting overhead lines. These values of power flows were needed in order to create a simulation model in DIgSILENT PowerFactory software package.

The simulation model of the Republic of Serbia is represented in detail while the surrounding systems are represented with equivalents respecting the values of totals and values of power flows on the interconnection lines which were calculated using software package PTI PSS@E. For the purposes of performing simulations models were developed for two characteristic regimes: winter maximum regime with load value of 7 882 MW in Serbia and summer maximum regime with load value of 5 205 MW in Serbia. For models in TYNDP peak values of load were obtained based on econometric method, using the predicted load factor. For each of these regimes power flow analyses were carried out in PowerFactory DIgSILENT software package [15].

In order to simulate JEQC device ability to commit generation units in a way to obtain maximum reactive power reserve Automatic Station Controller, Figure 6

and Figure 7 is modelled. The Station Control object is used in load flow calculations to simulate the behaviour of automatic control devices and operator action. It acts on sources of reactive power to achieve a target voltage at a certain bus.

Figure 6 Automatic Station Controller dialog in DIgSILENT Power Factory software package

Voltage control is done at a certain busbar. Controlled busbar is the busbar where the voltage will be controlled by adapting the reactive power. The user selects the controlled terminal. The controller uses the voltage set-point specified within the station controller.

Figure 7 Automatic Station Controller dialog for selection of the criteria for reactive power distribution

Contribution of the different reactive power sources to the control of the voltage is specified with an assigned contribution factor (Kp) that indicates the percentage to feed an actual value, in addition to its set point. This factor is calculated to maximise reactive reserve thus the contribution Kp factor is calculated to optimize the reactive power reserve of the sources.

The relationships between the station controller and the belonging sources is represented in Figure 8:

Figure 8 Relationships between the station controller and the belonging sources

The actual reactive power of each source is given by (4):

$$Q_i = Q_{stat,i} \quad (4)$$

where Q_i is the actual reactive power output of the source and $Q_{stat,i}$ is the reactive power of the source calculated by the station controller. For generators with connected step-up transformer the topologically connected HV busbar is used for the voltage controlled HV node.

If more than one transformer (generator) is in a group, the reactive power contribution of all generators not reaching the reactive power limit is controlled by the step-up transformer tap as follows:

$$K_{tot} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{Gen} Q_{m(i)} - \sum_{i=0}^{Gen} Q_{min(i)}}{\sum_{i=0}^{Gen} Q_{max(i)} - \sum_{i=0}^{Gen} Q_{min(i)}} \quad (5)$$

where Gen is the number of generators in the controlling logic group not reaching the reactive power limits and $Q_{m(i)}$ is the measured reactive power output of the generator "i".

$$K_i = \frac{K_{tot} * Q_{max(i)} + Q_{min(i)}}{1 + K_{tot}} \quad (6)$$

where $K(i)$ is the reactive power participation for generator "i".

The tap position is limited according to the minimum and maximum tap position of the transformer. A "pcl" (protocol) message is printed in the PowerFactory output window if the tap position is reaching the minimum or maximum position.

When the load flow is executed taking into account the reactive power limits if the controlled machines hit their respective reactive power limits the station controller is switched off [15].

3 Results

Through simulations voltage control at PCC of the plants SPP "Nikola Tesla A" and SPP "Nikola Tesla B", is being performed by automatically adjusting the levels of generated reactive power of the SPP's generators.

In Figure 9 generators power capability chart is shown and with numbers from 1 to 5 the following relevant values are denoted: 1 - rated operating values, 2 - maximum active power, 3 - maximum reactive power in underexcitation, 4 - maximum reactive power in overexcitation, 5 - maximum active power in underexcitation for rated active power.

Figure 9 SPP's generator power capability chart with relevant values denoted with numbers 1-5

For characteristic longterm planning work regimes (winter max, summer max and summer min) simulations were performed with and without Automatic Station Controller implemented. For each SPP Automatic Station Controller was set to a voltage reference value specified on the SPP's PCC with an option Maximise Reactive Power activated.

For each work regime for the voltage set value according to Table 1 load flow analysis were conducted in case when Automatic Station Controller was implemented in SPP and when Automatic Station Controller was out of service.

Table 1 Voltage reference value on the SPP's PCC

Generating Unit	Voltage [p.u]	Voltage [kV]
A1	0,997	219,373
A2	0,992	218,241
A3	0,985	216,715
A4	0,991	217,943
A5	1,021	408,736
A6	1,021	408,736
B1	1,019	402,051
B2	1,019	402,051

Each of those cases gave a solution with active and reactive power for voltage value set point that was predefined in accordance with Transmission System Operator instructions. In Figure 10, 11 and 12 difference

between reactive power provided in case Automatic Station Controller is in vs out of service for different longterm planning regimes is shown.

Figure 10 Difference between working case with Automatic Station Controller in/out of service for Winter max 2020 longterm planning work regime

Figure 11 Difference between working case with Automatic Station Controller in/out of service for Summer max 2020 longterm planning work regime

Figure 12 Difference between working case with Automatic Station Controller in/out of service for Summer min 2020 longterm planning work regime

In case of Summer max and Summer min it can be noticed that there is no difference in Reactive power provided by generating units. This is due to the fact that in summer period some of the generating units, in this case A1 and B2, are in scheduled maintenance meaning they are disconnected from the transmission system in that period. In the Winter max 2020 work regime all generating units of interest were in service. Units in the

initial state were committed in accordance with Adequacy methodology and Load forecast for year 2020.

4 Conclusion

The analysis carried out led to the following conclusions:

-by applying JEQC automation in order to manage voltage values and reactive power, it is possible to get the expansion of system operational limits as well as the improvement of the voltage quality and the security of supply

-with implementation of the JEQC automation the voltages vary in range of values in accordance with the Grid Code on a daily basis while ensuring the uniform and synchronized commitment of all participating generators which prevents generators from operating in forbidden areas of the capability chart

-the JEQC has a positive effect on the transmission system operation as an efficient tool for secondary voltage control obtaining maximum reactive power reserve at the same time.

Beside JEQC it is necessary to take into consideration coordination of all available control resources in a power system in order to optimize service quality.

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